

**citizen
science lab**

Margaret Gold

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European City of Science Leiden 2022

+ Programme Coordination 0.1 FTE
+ Project Staff 1 x 0.5 FTE

DO ALL THE
THINGS!

- UNESCO
- Citizen Science Global Partnership
- UNESCO OS & CS Community of Practice

- EU-Citizen.Science / ECSA
- Horizon Europe Criteria
- Mutual Learning Exercise

- NPOS – National Programme Open Science
- CS-NL – Citizen Science Nederland
- Rewards & Recognition Movement

- Grassroots Movements
- Citizen Participation
- European City of Science Leiden
2022

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Open Science

OPEN SCIENCE is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to

- make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone,
- to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and
- to **open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication**
 - to **societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.**
- It builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, **open engagement of societal actors** and **open dialogue with other knowledge Systems**

[HOME](#)

[ABOUT US](#)

[PROJECTS](#)

[NETWORK](#)

Supporting Partners

- UNESCO
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CITIZEN SCIENCE ELEVATING RESEARCH & INNOVATION THROUGH SOCIETAL ENGAGEMENT

Interaction between citizens, scientists and policy makers is essential to enrich research and innovation, and reinforce trust of society in science. I am proud of the hundreds of thousands involved citizens that already contributed to research and innovation and look forward to continue opening up research towards society and the world.

Mariya Gabriel *Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth*

Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science

Mutual learning exercises (MLE) focus on **specific R&I challenge** of interest to **MSs and ACs**

MLE on Citizen Science (CS) proposed from MSs to

- ✓ **strengthen their CS national policies and initiative** by exchanging lesson learnt and best practice
- ✓ exploit synergies and **upscale suitable (cross-) national CS initiatives** across the ERA

Exercise supported by EC Policy Support Facility and external experts

11 MSs/ACs: Germany, Slovenia, Austria, Belgium, France, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Italy, Sweden and Norway

CS MLE Topics:

1. Introduction and overview on citizen science
2. Ensuring good practices and impacts
3. Maximising the relevance and excellence of citizen science
4. Enabling environments and sustaining citizen science
5. Scaling up citizen science

“

What is an Enabling Environment?

the factors that enable Citizen Science initiatives to be launched, sustained, grow and thrive – and ultimately achieve their aimed-for impacts and outcomes

”

Legal & Policy Frameworks

Societal Dialogue

Internal Policies & Culture

FUNDING

Supporting (Data) Infrastructure

Capacity Building & Networks

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2022

NPOS Ambition 2030

2013 - 2021

2022 - 2030

2030

key lines of action

strategic goals

**2013
Ambitie 100%
Open Access**
The Dutch government takes the position that publicly funded research should be freely accessible.

**2018
Launch EOSC**
The symbolic launch of the European Open Science Cloud, a trusted, virtual, federated environment for sharing research data.

**2022
Launch NPOS
2030 Programme**
The NPOS2030 Programme marks a new phase in the transition to Open Science in the Netherlands.

**2017
Nationaal Plan
Open Science**
The presentation of the National Plan Open Science marks the launch of the NPOS.

**2021
UNESCO
recommendation
on Open Science**
UNESCO published their global Recommendation on Open Science to be adopted by the 193 Member States.

Towards societal engagement and participation

Towards inclusive and transparent scientific processes

Towards open scholarly communication

Towards FAIR and open research outputs

Close collaboration between knowledge institutions, government, industry, and citizens to strengthen science and optimise the processes of creating, sharing, and communicating knowledge for the benefit of society.

Inclusive, efficient, and transparent processes of scientific (co-)creation, evaluation, quality assurance and communication

Removal of barriers to reading and reusing all scientific output, so everyone can access sci-entific knowledge in a sustainable way and benefit from it

Products of and for knowledge creation, like data and software, being findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), and open in as far regulations allow

Open
Infrastructures

Support &
Training

Community
Engagement

Recognition &
Rewards

Policies &
Regulations

2020

nationaal
programma
**open
science**

*Kennis en krachten gebundeld –
citizen science in Nederland*

Wetenschap en samenleving in cocreatie

Eindverslag van de werkgroep Citizen Science

26 oktober 2020

NPOS (2020) Kennis en krachten gebundeld – citizen science in Nederland

tinyurl.com/nposreport

CS-NL

Citizen Science Nederland

key lines of action

Towards societal engagement and participation

Towards inclusive and transparent scientific processes

Towards open scholarly communication

Towards FAIR and open research outputs

Open
Infrastructures

Support &
Training

Community
Engagement

Recognition &
Rewards

Policies &
Regulations

Room for everyone's talent

towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics

> **Diversifying and vitalising career paths**

We enable more diversity in career paths and profiles for academics.

- UNESCO
- Citizen Science Global Partnership
- UNESCO OS & CS Community of Practice

- EU-Citizen.Science / ECSA
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- Mutual Learning Exercise

- NPOS – National Programme Open Science
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2022

Creating and circulating Knowledge in Resilient Societies

Open Science @ Leiden University

- 1 A transformation of the way we create and circulate knowledge
- 2 Why is a change necessary?
- 3 Our ambitions
- 4 Developing open knowledge practices: the five key areas
- 5 How are we going to do this?
- 6 Members of the Open Science Working Group
- 8 Best practices

citizen science lab

AGENDA

Vision

The CS Lab Strategic
Plan 2021 - 2025

Creating Space

Building Foundations

Embedding

2018

Founded

2019

0.2 fte staff

2020

2021

*1 fte Coordinator
Strategic Plan*

2022

*0.4 fte Coordinator
0.5 fte staff*

new home in CWTS

launched in 2018

BN DESTEM DINSdag 9 JULI 2013

ag voor ex

en Haarlem
server traag

en geijste het-
De landelijke
et om dit uit
derlan-
s spe-
Zij

utting / de Volkskrant

25%
ons
meens

...andvoorts
...den Boer
...Armstrong
...care
...Kreus
...Schoonderwerd
...Leiden
...Oeneas

...kosten
...hier en daar
...Mispel
...Sassenheim
...Arto Pohl
...Kouwdijk
...Arto Pohl

...De nieuwe stelling
...Geen uitpubliek
...Frank de Boer

gaan de lucht in

VANDAAG 3

50 De overheid heeft de maximaal toelaatbare hoeveelheid De dagelijkse norm is 50 microgram en die mag hooguit 35 dagen per jaar worden overschreden.

René Martens had verwacht een hogere concentratie fijnstof te meten.
foto Ron Magiels/het fotoburo

'Minder fijnstof in Breda dan verwacht'

door Maartje Huijben

BREDA - Nee, eerlijk gezegd had hij meer fijnstof verwacht dan dat woon relatief dicht gemeten. Ik en de spoorlijn. Ik ging ervan uit dat er daarom meer fijnstof in de lucht zou zitten. De hoeveelheid...
fijnstof van weinig tot veel. In de gelijkbaar, zij het dat op sommige gemeten. 'Ik ben geïnteresseerd in de wetenschap', verklaart Martens...
de avond leed hij een meting in zijn woonplaats Noorddorp (tussen Heerbaak en Oostdijk). 'Daar is het voor mij belangrijk om te weten, omdat Tata Steel mijn buur is.' Het resultaat: Ook heel helder

FOTOS: ANP

Massaal

Reportage
Fijnstofonderzoek
Het was lang wachten, een zo strakblauwe lucht dat fijnstof meten met duizenden smart meters tegelijk zin zou zijn. Maandag was het...

Van onze versier
Bard van de
LOPIK
in het
de 213

Lezers even wetenschappers

Honderd lezers van H1De Media deden gisteren mee met de nationale Fijnstofmeting van ipscn. Op twee momenten werd door de deelnemers met de iPhone - vooraf van een speciale app in de telefoon...
kon daarmee fijnstof worden gemeten. ipscn is een groot experiment over fijnstof waar iedereen ook een schat aan gegevens verzamelt. In september wordt het experiment, dat allen kan worden uitgeveerd bij een snakblat...
www.ipscn.nl

Is het tai chi of zijn ze bezig met wetenschap?

Duizenden mensen zagen gisteren een gunstige hock. Piet Wijdeman deed ten aanzien van de telefoon. Ze hielden de telefoon rechtop voor zich en bewogen de arm naar links en naar rechts. In nog een paar minuten kwam van deelnemer...
maar de wind waalde voor Tata uit. Het Wijdeman deed ten aanzien van de telefoon. Ze hielden de telefoon rechtop voor zich en bewogen de arm naar links en naar rechts. In nog een paar minuten kwam van deelnemer...
ook tot werkende oplossingen te komen. Ik ben dan ook benieuwd hoe de resultaten uiteindelijk in de praktijk vallen tot, wellicht nieuwsgierig, van allen kan worden uitgeveerd bij een snakblat...
www.ipscn.nl

Metropool

DINSdag 9 JULI 2013

Oeverplanten

Plastic Spotter

Erfgoed Gezocht

The Global Microplastic Project

Maps in the Crowd

COVID Radar

De Grote Griepmeting

SETTING A VISION

STRATEGIC PLAN 2021-2025

MARCH 2021

Citizen Science Lab, Leiden University
Frans Snik, Anne Land, Pedro Russo & Margaret Gold

**citizen
science
lab**

**citizen
science lab**

citizen science lab

The Citizen Science Lab brings together scientists, policy makers, citizens, and other stakeholders in **participatory research projects** that address scientific questions and/or urgent societal issues that can only be solved by actively involving volunteers in the scientific process.

We act as a **facilitator and incubator** to co-create new citizen science projects that connect society with science. And we function as a **knowledge hub** to build a collaborative and **transdisciplinary** knowledge-sharing network for citizen science practices in Leiden and across the Netherlands.

STRATEGIC PLAN 2021-2025

- 01 Establish a Leiden University knowledge hub and project incubator for citizen science
- 02 Design and implement the citizen science programme for the European City of (*Citizen*) Science 2022.
- 03 Co-create a transdisciplinary research initiative to address the UN SDGs
- 04 Embed CS practices into education, research and societal activities within Leiden and the surrounding region, for the long term
- 05 Establish the CSLab as a cornerstone of the nascent Dutch National Platform for Citizen Science

CREATING SPACE

2021

01 ✓ We have established a knowledge hub and project incubator for citizen science, currently based within the Astronomy & Society Group, that supports colleagues across all faculties of the University. Publications in 2021 include Royal Society Open Science, Springer Sustainability Science, Journal of Science Communication, and the Journal of Environment Management

02 ✓ We are leading the CS Programme of 'Seeing Stars in Leiden', the Postbus 71 initiative to channel science Q&A, and a 'Participate' programme of activities to promote existing and new Citizen Science projects and initiatives that are relevant to the 365-day themes, during the European City of Science Leiden 2022 festivities.

03 ✓ We are actively collaborating and 'originating' new transdisciplinary projects with EUniwel partners, Leids Preventie Akkoord partners, Leren Met de Stad, (and more) that are directly relevant to the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Questions from residents coming into Postbus 71 will be filtered for a potential new 'Plastic Spotter' style CS project.

04 ✓ The Honours Academy Impact Challenge MSc course embeds CS practices in the curriculum and addresses challenges framed within the 'Duurzaamste Kilometer van Nederland' initiative together with Gemeente Leiden and other local partners. Workshops and training sessions delivered in the faculties support CS practices in research.

05 ✓ The Coordinator of the CS Lab also leads the CS Programme Line within NPOS, developing the Citizen Science strategy for the Netherlands towards 2030, and placing Leiden University as a cornerstone of the nascent Dutch National Platform for Citizen Science.

01 **GOAL 1:** Establish a Leiden University knowledge hub and project incubator for citizen science

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BUILDING FOUNDATIONS

2022

The screenshot shows a webpage from Leiden University. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Leiden University', 'Students', 'Staff members', 'Organisational structure', and 'Library'. Below this is the university logo and a search bar. A secondary navigation bar contains links for 'Home', 'Research', 'Education', 'Academic staff', 'About us', 'Collaboration', 'Faculties', 'Campus The Hague', 'Alumni', and 'Library'. The main content area features a breadcrumb trail: 'Home > News > A call about: the Citizen Science Lab'. A large image shows a mailbox labeled 'Postbus 71.nl' with a colorful QR code and the text 'Stel hier je vraag'. The article title is 'A call about: the Citizen Science Lab', dated '11 January 2022'. The text describes Leiden's status as European City of Science in 2022 and the role of Postbus 71. A sidebar on the right includes 'Academic staff' (Margaret Gold), 'See also' (Leiden European City of Science 2022, Postbus 71), and a 'Dossier Leiden2022' section with a colorful geometric logo.

Leiden University | Students | Staff members | Organisational structure | Library

Universiteit Leiden

Search for subject or person | All categories | Nederlands | English

Home | Research | Education | Academic staff | About us | Collaboration | Faculties | Campus The Hague | Alumni | Library

Home > News > A call about: the Citizen Science Lab

A call about: the Citizen Science Lab

11 January 2022

Leiden is European City of Science in 2022 and this will be celebrated under the name Leiden2022. During Leiden2022, various activities will be organised, such as lectures, workshops, excursions and exhibitions. On the occasion of Leiden2022, Postbus 71 will be opened: the place to go if you have any questions about science. Margaret Gold, coordinator of the Citizen Science Lab, answered three questions about the Citizen Science Lab activities during Leiden2022.

What is the Citizen Science Lab, and what is its role during Leiden2022?

The Citizen Science Lab is a Knowledge Hub and Project Incubator that is based within the Science Faculty of Leiden University, but works with all faculties and domains of research to connect citizens and societal actors together with scientists in collaborative research initiatives that have an impact on both knowledge and society. Throughout the year we will be running Postbus 71 – the place for all residents and visitors to send those curiosity-sparked questions that either come from the daily themes of 'Kennis door de Wijken' (Knowledge through the Neighbourhoods) or are things that you've always wondered about. We'll play postmaster with those questions to ask research colleagues at the University, share at events throughout the year on those topics, or bring up in the conversations on Radio Weetlust. But we are also keeping our eyes open for questions to which we can answer 'Let's go find out!' We would love to start a new Citizen Science research project in collaboration with Leiden residents on a topic that is relevant to the city and our living environment.

What kind of questions have you already received for Postbus 71?

We are still just getting the word out, but already some fantastic questions have come in. 8 year-old Michiel has asked us why he doesn't always find his mother's cooking tasty. We'll ask these questions of our research colleagues on the 16th of October when the day theme will be 'Voedsel', but in the meantime we've shared an interesting article in *WRM? Magazine* about how our tastebuds and other senses (and our brains!) can influence how we experience the taste of food.

Academic staff
Margaret Gold
Research Staff Member

See also
Leiden European City of Science 2022
Postbus 71

Dossier Leiden2022
Leiden is European City of Science 2022

European
City of Science
Leiden2022

365 dagen nieuwsgierig

GOAL 2: Design and implement the citizen science programme for the 2022 European City of (Citizen) Science.

02

Who knows the unknown?

The unknown as an infinitely curiosity-inducing source of inspiration for science. We have no view of 97% of the universe. 95% of the oceans are still completely unknown to us. We have not yet mapped 85% of all species on earth. We still know very little about the human brain... A tempting perspective of not yet knowing. Food for big questions.

European City of Science Leiden2022

22 Big Questions

De 22 grote vragen van 2022

- WELKE VRAAG HOUDT JOU BEZIG?
- WAAROM WILLEN WI WETEN?
- WAT WAS ER VOOR HET BEGIN?
- HOEVEEL DIMENSIES ZIJN ER?
- KUNNEN WE OOI TIJDEREIZEN?
- HOE LANG ZIJN WE NOG ALLEEN?
- IS ER EEN THEORIE VAN ALLES?
- WAT KUNNEN WE NOG NIET BEREKENEN?
- WAT MAAKT DAT DE AARDE DRAAIT?
- KUNNEN MENSEN, DIER EN NATUUR IN BALANS MET ELKAAR BESTAAN?
- WAT IS EEN VRAAG?
- WAAROM IS WETENSCHAP ZO BELANGRIJK?
- HOE HOUDEN WE WETENSCHAP GEZOND?
- HOE OPEN IS EN KAN ZIJN?
- WAT IS DE ROL VAN KUNST?
- HOE GEVEN WE DE TOEKOMST VORM?
- HOE OUD KUNNEN WE WORDEN?
- HOE WERKT ONS BREIN?
- WYSIWYG?
- WAT MAAKT ONS MENS?
- IS IEDEREEN GELIJK?
- WELKE VRAAG IS NOG DOOR NIEMAND GEFORMULEERD?

Kennis door de Wijken

POSTBUS 71 POSTMASTER

- Q&A on Radio Weetlust
- Q&A on @Postbus71
- Q&A on Leiden2022.nl
- Q&A at Festiwell
- Q&A at ESOF2022
- Q&A 'Kennis door de Wijken' Events

Questions filtered for CS applicability
Multi-stakeholder engagement

Co-Design

Citizen Science Voor & Door de Wijken

Let's go find out !!

Year of Events

365

European
City of Science
Leiden2022

Co-funded by
the European Union

Meta Knol
Leiden2022

BY

GOAL 2: Design and implement the citizen science programme for the 2022 European City of (Citizen) Science.

02

European
City of Science
Leiden2022

Kennis
door de
Wijken

'DHZ' Crowdsourcing
Research Questions

'Moeder Natuur'
Bioblitz

'Citizen Science'
Show & Tell

'Jungle'
Bioblitz

citizen
science lab

Seeing Stars Leiden

....Lichten Uit, Sterren Aan...

Citizen Science Participation

CS for Climate Change Impact on Nature

The logo for De NestWacht features a green circle with a lightbulb icon. To its right is a photograph of three wooden birdhouses in blue, white, and green. Above the birdhouses are icons for wind, water, sun, and a factory. Below the photo are logos for TU Delft, Science Centre Delft, Naturalls Academy College, and citizen science lab.

The logo for The Wardrobe Project features a blue circle with a lightbulb icon. To its right is a circular diagram with a globe at the top, a recycling symbol at the bottom left, and the number 12 in a brown circle at the bottom right. Arrows connect the globe, the recycling symbol, and the number 12.

CS for Sustainable Clothing Consumption

STEM Learning through CS Research in the Classroom

The Lil scientist logo features a blue graduation cap and an orange character. Below it are logos for de jonge akademie and imcweekendschool. To the right is a grey circle with a lightbulb icon.

The euniwell logo features the text 'euni' in blue and 'well' in purple. To the right is a purple circle with a lightbulb icon.

CS for Well Being / Mental Health in collaboration with Students

Waar ben je naar op zoek? 2021-2022 Zoeken

Leiden Municipality Challenge: Citizen Science and The Most Sustainable Kilometre

**DRZM SITE
KM van NL**

Een uitnodiging tot samenwerking aan een duurzame toekomst voor Leiden

We werken samen aan de (her)ontwikkeling van een complex en dynamisch gebied; het nieuwe Stationsgebied en de transformatie van de Schipholweg in Leiden. Dit wordt een aantrekkelijke plek om te wonen en werken, rondom een sterke mobiliteitsknoop. Daarbij zijn we ons bewust van onze voorbeeldfunctie in deze prominente gebiedsontwikkelingen. We nemen onze verantwoordelijkheid, en gaan voorop in verduurzaming, het creëren van een gezonder leefmilieu en het toekomstproof maken van het Stationsgebied / de Schipholweg. Door met elkaar te werken aan kansrijke duurzame cases, wordt de verduurzaming van deze gebiedsontwikkelingen versneld. Zo zijn we gezamenlijk in 2025 de Duurzaamste Kilometer van Nederland.

Labels on map: DROGE VOETEN, AFVAL BESTAAT NIET, ZONNE-ENERGIE VOOR IEDEREEN, SLIJME WARMTE EN KOUDE, SCHONE MOBILITEIT DELEN, DIVERS GROEN, MASTER PLAN STATIONSGBIED, SCHIPHOLWEG, LEIDEN CS.

Periode:	<input type="checkbox"/>
Docenten:	Dr. Anne Land-Zandstra Dr. Margaret Gold Researchers of The Young Academy Leiden
Credits:	10 EC
Niveau:	600
Locatie:	Leiden
Voertaal:	Engels

GOAL 4: Embed CS practices into education, research and societal activities within Leiden and the surrounding region, for the long term

04

Creating and circulating Knowledge in Resilient Societies

Open Science @ Leiden University

- 1 A transformation of the way we create and circulate knowledge
- 2 Why is a change necessary?
- 3 Our ambitions
- 4 Developing open knowledge practices: the five key areas
- 5 How are we going to do this?
- 6 Members of the Open Science Working Group
- 8 Best practices

Discover the world at Leiden University

GOAL 4: Embed CS practices into education, research and societal activities within Leiden and the surrounding region, for the long term

04

Embedding in the University

2023

Leiden University | Students | Staff members | Organisational structure | Library

Universiteit Leiden

Search for subject or person | All categories | Nederlands | English

Research | Education | Academic staff | About us | Collaboration | Faculties | Campus The Hague | Alumni | Library

Home > About us > Profile > Leiden University Strategy

Leiden University Strategy

In our new strategic plan (Innovating and Connecting – 2022-2027) we focus on stronger connections: between disciplines, with society and within our university community.

Our ambitions

To strengthen the connections between disciplines, between the University and society, and within our university community, we will work in the coming years on the following six strategic ambitions:

- Room for innovation**
Realising change and innovation requires space. To create this scarce space, we will take various measures to make the workload manageable and to provide more opportunities for our staff to pursue their ambitions.
- Pioneering interdisciplinary research and teaching**
We will maintain the high standard of our individual disciplines, and from this firm basis will inspire more interdisciplinary collaboration. We will ensure there is also space for independent and fundamental research within our interdisciplinary research.
- Future-proof student development**
Our vision on teaching and learning (Learning@LeidenUniversity 2017-2023) is based on inquiry-based learning so that students can develop within an enriching academic environment. We will increase our activities in the area of personal and professional development during and after their initial studies and encourage them to develop and reflect – a whole life long.

Innovating and Connecting

See our new strategic plan here

- About us
- Profile
 - Leiden University Strategy**
 - International profile
 - History
 - Sustainability
 - Diversity and inclusion
 - Two cities
 - Management and organisation
 - Impact
 - Our alumni
 - Support us
 - Facts and figures
 - Working at Leiden University
 - Visit us
 - Contact

citizen science lab

VISION

In **2025**, Leiden University is an *innovative* pioneer of *collaborative citizen science* initiatives that *connect* science and society in *transdisciplinary* research to address urgent scientific & societal challenges together.

citizen science lab

Margaret Gold
info@citscilab.org

**citizen
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